

Inferring multi-cue migratory navigation in geese using inverse reinforcement learning

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Abstract. Understanding how birds integrate multiple environmental cues during migration remains challenging. In this study, we apply maximum entropy inverse reinforcement learning (IRL) to GPS trajectories from 122 greater white-fronted geese (*Anser albifrons*) to infer migratory navigation strategies. Using geomagnetic, atmospheric, and visual landmark features as potential cues, migration is modelled as a reward-based decision-making process. The results indicate a prominent role of geomagnetic variation and preferences for flat coastal corridors and favourable wind conditions. Our findings demonstrate the potential of IRL as a data-driven approach for studying multi-cue migratory navigation in movement ecology.

Submission Type. model, analysis, case study

BoK Concepts. [GC2] Spatial simulation modelling, [AM5] Basic analytical methods

Keywords. bird migration, inverse reinforcement learning, navigational cues, movement ecology, spatial-temporal trajectory analysis

1 Introduction

Migratory birds use various cues for navigation during their long journeys, such as geomagnetic field and visual landmarks (Mouritsen, 2018). They are also affected by atmospheric conditions (Shamoun-Baranes et al., 2017). Despite extensive research, how birds integrate and prioritize these cues remains a subject of debate.

Inverse reinforcement learning (IRL) is a machine learning technique that infers an agent’s preferences from observed behaviour by representing them as a reward function linked to internal and external conditions (Arora and Doshi, 2021). Unlike reinforcement learning (RL),

which executes optimal behaviour by maximizing a predefined reward function, IRL works in reverse by assuming the observed behaviour is already optimal and recovering the reward function that could generate it. This makes IRL valuable for problems with limited domain knowledge such as driving planning (Liu et al., 2023) and human behaviour prediction (Ye et al., 2024), where manually specifying reward functions is often inaccurate or intractable.

Over the past two decades, the increasing accessibility of GPS has enabled high-resolution tracking of animal movement, making it possible to apply data-driven approaches such as IRL to the study of animal migration (Demšar et al., 2025). Using greater white-fronted geese (*Anser albifrons*) as a study species, we model the migration process based on geese GPS tracking data and multiple environmental features. Our research explores the potential of IRL to reveal how birds integrate different cues and aims to uncover the navigational strategies underlying their migratory behaviours.

2 Methods

2.1 Study species and environmental features

The geese follow an annual migratory cycle, moving between their wintering areas in the Netherlands and their breeding sites in northern Russia. We focus on the autumn migration, comprising GPS tracking data from 122 geese collected between 2014 and 2025. We consider geomagnetic variation (intensity change, ΔF ; inclination change, ΔI ; apparent inclination change, $\Delta I'$), atmospheric conditions (tailwind, headwind, crosswind left, and crosswind right), and visual landmarks (distance to coastline, land-sea mask, and elevation) as potential navigational cues used by the geese.

Figure 1. Workflow of the methods.

2.2 Data preprocessing

As our analysis focuses on navigation during flight, we first extracted stopovers along the migration routes and segmented the complete trajectories into flight segments. Furthermore, we resampled both flight segments and environmental features to a unified spatial-temporal resolution. This procedure allowed us to construct a state space suitable for training the IRL model.

2.3 Maximum entropy IRL

We applied maximum entropy IRL to infer the underlying reward structure over environmental features. This framework models expert behaviour by estimating a global state-action distribution that maximizes entropy, subject to feature expectation constraints derived from observed trajectories (Liu et al., 2023). As a result, it naturally accommodates both near-optimal and stochastic decision-making, which is particularly suitable for modelling animal movement. Additionally, the IRL model yields a policy that defines action probabilities at each state. This enables us to characterise the migration strategies of geese across different spatial-temporal contexts within the state space.

2.4 Model evaluation

The policy was used to generate simulated trajectories via apprenticeship learning, initialized from the same start states as the flight segments in the test set. To quantitatively evaluate model performance, we compared the simulated trajectories with the test segments using three complementary metrics: mean distance, dynamic time warping (DTW), and dynamic interaction index (DI). These metrics capture trajectory similarity in geographic distance, spatial-temporal alignment, and movement direction, respectively. An overview of the workflow is shown in Fig. 1

2.5 Data and Software Availability

The work is currently ongoing. The IRL model code and the associated datasets (including flight segments and features for model training and evaluation) will be made publicly available upon publication of the full research paper through Zenodo and GitHub repositories.

3 Results

The reward map shows elevated values along the geese’s autumn migratory corridor, with higher rewards concentrated in nesting sites, stopovers, and wintering areas along the North Sea and Baltic coasts and in Yamal. These regions align with the final sections of the geese flight segments, reflecting the migratory preferences captured by the IRL model (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Reward map derived from the IRL.

Among the considered features, ΔF and ΔI exhibit relatively higher accumulated rewards than other features, indicating a prominent role of geomagnetic cue in migration. The landmark features are associated with negative rewards, reflecting a preference for flat coastal areas. For atmospheric conditions, tailwind exhibits positive and higher accumulated rewards, whereas headwind and crosswind are associated with negative rewards, suggesting the geese optimize for tailwind

assistance while avoiding strong headwind and crosswind conditions (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Accumulated rewards of selected features.

The IRL policy reproduces the main migratory corridor and generates simulated trajectories that are generally consistent with the GPS tracks (Fig. 4). A small number of inland-deviating trajectories show lower similarity values, indicating potential model limitations and motivating further investigation into additional environmental features or individual-specific factors.

Figure 4. Example of trajectory simulation results for flight segment with ID 1013-8.

4 Conclusions

Although IRL has been explored in related domains, its application in animal movement remains limited. In this study, we demonstrate that IRL can be used to reproduce bird migratory corridors and generate trajectories consistent with observed GPS tracks. While this work is still exploratory, the results provide promising evidence that data-driven approaches such as IRL can capture essential environmental preferences and replicate migratory behaviour from movement trajectories.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

No generative AI was used in this manuscript.

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